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DIFFERENCE BETWEEN CONCEPTS OF ACQUISITION AND LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

Zaripova Shakarjon Narimon qizi

Urganch davlat universiteti

Ingliz til va adabiyoti

kafedrasi stajor-o'qituvchisi

Abstract: *The article presents learning process of obtaining foreign language, finding its characteristics including contradictions between concepts of acquisition with learning other language.*

Key words: *concept, acquisition, perspectives, interrelationship, conscious, methodology, subconscious, contradiction.*

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada chet tillarni ongli va ongsiz ravishda o'rganish jarayonidagi farqlarning foydali va samarali usullari ko'rib chiqiladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *tushuncha, egallash, yaratish, o'zaro aloqadorlik, ongli, metodologiya, ongsiz, ziddiyatlar.*

Аннотация: *В статье представлен процесс обучения овладению иностранным языком, выявлены его восприятия, в том числе противоречия между понятиями овладения иностранным языком и изучением другого языка.*

Ключевые слова: *понятие, приобретение, перспективы, взаимосвязь, сознание, методология, подсознание, противоречие.*

Language is suggested to be one of the most essential means we use to inform ideas to interlocutor. The acquisition of language continues to be the most fascinating aspect of individuals development. Beginning from initial monosyllabic statements to the utilization of complicated, nuanced and context-based patterns, and both the progress stage and the language acquisition way have been the main idea of unnumbered researches in evolutionary linguistics, psychology and pedagogy. The use of two and more languages provides human to form variable integrated networks for the establishment of new learning experiences.

As it is claimed by Krashen, to obtain communication means is to acquire the language as do children, like acquiring his/her mother tongue without conscious attention to the language system. Beside this, gaining a language is to concentrate on the formality and the rules of a particular language. Moreover, the basic varieties are considered to be the other factors that impact both first language acquisition and second one, such as the cognitive and environmental aspects.

The contemporary issues of worldwide evolutionary tendency punctuates the main significance in maintained improvement, that is to meet the needs of the present, without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs” (Zimmermann, 2003: 9). In other words, this is an individual who is ready to evolve the system of external and internal perspectives, and in this case the above mentioned prospects become the essential circumstances for the steady identity to develop. Hence, the life requirement to promote the framework of two vision, being exactly: external and internal, defines the research methodology of the interaction between language acquisition and learning in the pedagogical discourse, as particular emphasis was introduced in Figure 1 by Ahrens (2010: 7). If the components in two syntheses are analysed, we point out the variance between external and internal perspectives addressing state of the trainees. In most cases, in external perspectives it is noticed that the learners' approach to studying language consciously, and study the language systematically. The following illustration points out the alteration of synthesis.

Figure 1. Developing the system of external and internal perspectives as a life necessity

Although, in real life experience it is shown that a viable individual is frequently grasped from one of these perspectives: by the side of internal potentials stressing cognition, from the external perspective emphasizing societal link and revealing a balance between the external and internal perspectives. That's why, the proper suggestion included to the topic is a welfare result in which the essential requirement is interaction of two people-dialogue. In order to search for the relationship between language acquisition and language learning assumes a way of reviewing the impact of crucial concepts "language acquisition", "language learning", "mother tongue" and "foreign language", and manifesting the idea regarding how main concepts are influential in external and internal progressing systems.

As a beginning stage, the perception of native language occurs with spontaneous, free usage of communication and as the time pasts, it begins to develop in the conscious way by linguistic form, regarding the development of foreign, second language occurs consciously and begins to develop spontaneously, free speech. Exactly speaking, the we begin communicating in mother tongue spontaneously, then learn the formal language, what about the foreign one, it is started as a formal language, then becomes

spontaneous. Therefore to review the spontaneous, academic and professional concepts are the discussion of native, foreign and professional languages. Precisely speaking, professional language is a native language which is learned for specific purposes. In this way, research community draws the attention that the link between language acquisition and language learning is important in the module of development: “scientific and spontaneous learning concepts are absolutely different, but at some teaching and learning processes they are similar”. Consequently, the prevalence of spontaneous concept gaining defines the individual's actual development level, and the rate of academic concept acquiring discloses the individual's nearest zone of growth within Vygotsky's Theory on the Proximal Zone of Development (Vigotskiy, 2002: 257).

It is the fact, the acquisition-learning distinction is probably the most foundational hypotheses of all times to be presented there. It maintains that adults have two particular and autonomous technique to develop the competence in a second language. The former way is a language acquisition, a similar process to identical way, where children raise their capabilities in the first language. We are, as a rule, unconsciously know the rules of the language we acquire. But instead of that, we have a "intuition" for correct usage of language. Grammatical structured sentences "sound" right and if it is not, we "feel" it right, and mistakes feel wrong, Even if the people do not the appropriate grammar rules in such cases. Including the other ways of forming the language, for example informal learning, implicit language acquisition and learning naturally.

The next manner to expand the competence in a second language by learning. The term learning is usually used for conscious learning process, where the learners are aware of grammar rules, formal language and being able to understand and use them in a needed way. In non-technical expression, learning is "knowing regarding" languages, noted to majority of people as "grammar", or "rules". Some synonyms involve formal knowledge of the language and explicit learning.

Here it should be mentioned that some second language theorists have estimated that children obtain, while elders can just learn. The learning/acquisition hypothesis consider, thus, that adults acquire too, that the capability to "picking-up" languages do not disappear at virility. This does not mean that elder people would all the time be able to reach like native levels in a second-foreign language. So, it mean that adults could access the similar natural "language acquisition devices" that children utilize. As it is suggested we shall see later, acquiring the language is an utterly important process in the adult. The correction of mistakes has tiny or not effect in subconscious acquisition, but this is thought to be handy for conscious study. The error correction admittedly helpful the learner to introduce or "sort out" the necessary form of rules. If, for instance, the student of English language as a second language says "I does my homework every day", and the teacher checks and corrects him/her by rehearsing the utterance in a right way, the scholars is assumed to actualize that the "s" ending follows with the third human and not the former person, and vary his or her conscious intellectual representations of the rule. This appears sensible, but it is not explicitly whether mistakes correction have this impact in real practice (Long, 1997).

Prove from children language acquiring acknowledge the error correction does not impact acquisition to some great extent. Brown with his colleagues have shown that people actually rectify just a small parts of the child's language (infrequent pronunciation issues, verbs, and dirty language!). To conclude from these researches that parents behaviour far more to the verity value of that the child is saying more than to the form. For example, the sentence by Brown, and Bellugi (2004) reports that:

Mother curl my hair

"was proved, because her mother was, actually, curling daughter's hair" (p. 330).

On the other hand:

Walt Disney come on on Tuesday was corrected by its syntactic accuracy, since Walt Disney, in fact, came on TV on Monday. Brown ends up with the point that it seems to be "correct valued rather than syntactic, well-formed identity that chiefly manages an explicit verbal reinforcement by parents which renders deeply paradoxical

the factors that the typical product of such a practical scheme is an adult whose speaking skills is highly structured but not notably correct" (p. 330). The acquisition-learning diversity might not be unique for second language acquisition. Certainly "learn" little parts of our first language in schools and same distinction has been made in another domain.

By a grammatical syllabus, each structure is represented just once. If a student misses this, is absent, is not giving attention, or if there easily has not been enough pragmatics (input), the student can have to wait for next year, when all structures are viewed one more time. On the other hand, roughly-tuned input lets for natural review.

A grammatical syllabus supposes that we are aware of the order of acquisition. Accordingly, scholar Krashen has no such assumption is necessary which we rely on the input, on roughly tuned native communication. Research which has been hold over the decade has confirmed that a variants of affective variables refer to success in second language learning. Most of those studied can be replaced into one of these three categories:

1. Motivation. Performers who are highly motivation generally try to do better in second language acquisition (normally, but not all the time, "integrative") that's` why it is necessary to encourage learners with the help of different activities.
2. Self-confidence. It plays a huge role in every sphere, so in the second language performance and requires teachers to improve learners` confidence, learners` autonomy.
3. Anxiety. Low anxiety arises to be conducive in second language acquisition, however measured as individual or classroom anxiety. In some places we could be the witness that the attitudinal facts relate directly to obtaining and not to learning, while they tend to present stronger interrelationships to second language development when speech-type tests are used, which that tap the required rather than the accepted systems, and when students take the test to have used the language in "acquisition" situations, where comprehensible input was plentiful.

As it was claimed before, the past research methods emphasize that acquisition of language and learning strategies put more focus on determining strategic ways and characteristics in the differentiation of acquiring language, while more current studies have attempted to demonstrate language learning manners and classify strategies which are used by language obtainers in the process of learning. In addition, by providing a huge number of researches, educators have revealed that there is a link between the utilization and choice of learning strategies and variables contexts of them, learner characteristics, experiences, language proficiency and educational backgrounds. The researchers came to the conclusion that by knowing information regarding differences between acquisition and learning facilitate and develop learners knowledge in different ways. It is also claimed that a proximate link is between language proficiency and its achievement in learning.

References

1. Maslo, E. (2007) Transformative Learning Space for Life-Long Foreign Languages Learning. International Nordic-Baltic Region Conference of FIPLV Innovations in Language Teaching and Learning in the Multicultural Context 15- 16th June, 2007, Riga, Latvia.
2. Cohen, A.D. & Scott, K., 1996: A synthesis of approaches to assessing language learning strategies. In R. Oxford (Ed.), *Language Learning Strategies Around the World: Cross- cultural Perspectives* (pp. 89-106). Manoa: University of Hawaii Press.
3. Robbins, D. (2007) Vygotsky's and Leontiev's Non-classical Psychology Related to Second Language Acquisition. International Nordic-Baltic Region Conference of FIPLV Innovations in Language Teaching and Learning in the Multicultural Context 15-16th June, 2007, Riga, Latvia.
4. Vygotsky, L. (1934/1962) *Thought and Language. The Development of Scientific Concepts in Childhood* Cambridge, MS: MIT.
5. Ариян, М.А. Ключевые компетенции в процессе обучения иностранному языку // *Иностранные языки в школе*. М.: Просвещение, 2005. №6. С. 28-31.
6. Артемов, В.А. *Психология обучения иностранным языкам*. М. 1969. 279с.